

Application Stack running at FMI/CSC, preparation of System Stack T3.2 Team

Milestone MS2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 675191

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Type: Report published in the website

Delivery date Annex 1 (DoA) month 9

Means of verifications: Summer School operational

Achieved: Yes, with some limitations, see in the text.

Comments: A first version on D3.7 is already available.

Introduction

This document supports the work on the Task 3.1.3 of the Work Package 3 (Usability) of the Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe (ESiWACE) project. The goal of this task is to test the installation process of the common Earth System Modelling (ESM) Software Environment, which was specified by the team working on the Task 3.1.2, at the Centre for Scientific Computing¹ (CSC) in Finland. This action was planned to be done in the context of the Third European Earth System and Climate Modelling School (3rd E2SCMS), held in Helsinki, 9-21 June 2016 and evaluated by the students and the staff. 28 students, of which 16 were male and 5 non-EU, participated. Eighteen full lectures were given, and about 440 person-hours were spent on one-to-one tutorials. Participants were very satisfied by the school providing insightful recommendations for the next school, too. The result of the task is to be provided to the team working on the Task 3.2 to support their efforts on the development of a methodology for maintaining a portable high-performance computing (HPC) software stack that will support the exploitation of the pan-European HPC infrastructure and prepare for the exascale demonstrators.

Context

Initiated by the European Network for Earth System modelling (ENES) with support of the second phase project on the Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling² (IS-ENES2) funded by the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration, the 3rd E2SCMS was open to early career scientists (advanced PhD candidates, postdoctoral scientists, scientific programmers) who are affiliated with European research institutions. The school was supported by international experts in Earth system and climate modelling ensuring an advanced and stimulating learning environment. The course began with a series of lectures, which were followed by practical sessions where participants applied what they had learnt by analysing the results of their own Earth system simulations. In this part of the course three well established Earth System Models were used: HadCM3 (FAMOUS), MPI-ESM, and EC-Earth.

Technical considerations

Three different models were presented in the school and used to carry on student assignments:

- HadCM3 (FAMOUS): FAMOUS is a low resolution Earth-System model, based on an early version of the Unified Model (vn4.5), which has been used extensively for educational and training purposes. Its advantage lies primarily in its ability to run long climate integrations with minimal compute resource requirements, but also in its very weak dependence on third party software. It has the disadvantage of being tied to an old infrastructure not based on modern software management and engineering practices, and not using a modern workflow scheduler – its job submission system is hosted on a machine located at Reading University and is entirely unsuitable for installation elsewhere by reason of its legacy structure and significant support requirements. However, its use is simple enough that providing access to it is not considered problematic for driving FAMOUS in a training environment.

¹ <https://www.csc.fi/>

² <http://is.enes.org>

- MPI-ESM: Earth system model of Max Planck Institute is a comprehensive Earth-System Model. It couples – via OASIS – the ocean, atmosphere and land surface through the exchange of energy, momentum, water and important trace gases such as carbon dioxide. The MPI-ESM was used as the basis for Max Planck Institute’s contribution to the fifth phase of the coupled model intercomparison project (CMIP5), and is the current workhorse of the institute scientists. It is the successor of the previous ECHAM5/MPIOM coupled model, which was used for the CMIP3 project, and for the internal Millennium project.
- EC-Earth 3.1: EC-Earth is developed as part of a Europe-wide consortium thus promoting international cooperation and access to wide knowledge and data base. It further enables fruitful interactions between academic institutions and the European climate impact community. The configuration used (GCM) is runs with the NEMO ocean model, the IFS atmospheric model and OASIS coupler for exchanging fields.

HadCM3 (FAMOUS) and MPI-ESM have a coarse resolution configuration, which means the students were able to get results during the first days of the summer school. This was not the case for the EC-Earth model, where the smallest available configuration is T255L91-ORCA1. This configuration takes quite some time to execute: to get one hundred years of outputs, the minimum amount of simulated years to get useful results for the students, can take approximately 10 days of intensive computing (i.e. ~ 10 SYPD). This means that the results had to be computed before the school in the home HPC cluster (in this case Mare Nostrum 3 in Barcelona) and stored in an archive system for further analysis.

Moreover, the school was organized to analyse the outputs produced by six assignments based on perturbations in the source code of the model. These assignments were not easy to perform and they require deep knowledge of the code and some days of preparation and validation of the results. In the case of EC-Earth this situation was even more difficult because it was necessary to accumulate knowledge from different institutions to solve the assignments. This work had been done by Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) in collaboration with Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI).

In the remainder of this report we will not consider EC-Earth any further.

Time and organizational constraints

The main constraint which had a strong impact on this task was the rescheduling of the summer school. Originally the school was planned for September 2016, and the tasks of ESIWACE were set to be accomplished by this date. Unfortunately, due to local organization issues, the school was moved to June 2016. This rescheduling dramatically shortened the time to accomplish the installations, and the final execution of the exercises had the highest priority against other tasks.

An additional constraint found during the school was the lack of resources available to carry out this kind of training from the EC-Earth community. The effort of setting up the models with the non-standard configurations, running the simulations, moving and preparing outputs, and staying for two weeks in the school was done in kind by the institutions so it was difficult to find people available to participate.

When working remotely, access to the different HPC resources is a key aspect in the organisation of the school. Many activities were performed remotely so the network connection had to be fast, smooth and with the lowest possible lag. There are different security policies for each computing facility that can reduce users' productivity by introducing additional constraints, which was the case during the school.

Another aspect to keep in mind is the reluctance scientists show – understandably enough - to change their working environments. Many people who work with models are familiar with a particular system and the skills they have are based on the corresponding architecture, environment, and queuing system. Changing these parameters makes scientists less productive as is the case when they have to use an unknown machine.

Work done in the context of the school

Two supercomputers were offered by the Finnish CSC to run the experiments of the 3rdE2SCMS. The first one, named Taito, consists of 407 Apollo 6000 XL230a G9 server blades (each with two twelve core Intel Haswell E5-2690v3 CPUs) and 576 HP ProLiant SL230s servers (each with two eight core Intel Xeon 2.6 GHz E5-2670 CPUs). It is also aided by a Bull B715 cluster, which has 36 and 46 nodes with Nvidia Kepler K40 GPGPUs and Intel Xeon Phi 7120X coprocessors respectively. The cluster is intended for serial (single core) and small to medium-size parallel jobs that utilize less than 256 computing cores. There are also 42 "fat nodes" for jobs requiring a large amount of memory.

The second one, Sisu, is a Cray XC40 Supercomputer with 1688 compute nodes (each with two twelve core Intel Xeon E5-2690v3 2,6GHz CPUs). Sisu is targeted for massively parallel applications that can effectively run on hundreds to thousands of compute cores in parallel³.

As a result of the constraints described above, the only model that was run on the resources of the CSC during the school was MPI-ESM 1. Features of Sisu made it the natural choice for these experiments.

MPI-ESM1

The first step to get MPI-ESM1 to run on Sisu was to adapt the model's building process (the conversion of source code into executables) to the new software environment. The model depends on several third party libraries and the way they are configured and stored in a filesystem varies from one machine to another. There are common software tools like Autotools⁴ and CMake⁵ that help to overcome these issues but the complexity of ESM models is often too high to enable a transparent building process without additional tools. MPI-ESM1 includes an additional script (an executable file) that invokes configuration scripts (generated with Autotools) of the model's components in a consistent way (i.e. the components are configured in a particular order and against the same system libraries). This script is a single entry point to the model building system and is intended to hide the complexity of the deployment process from users. Our task was to extend the configuration script, so it would work in a different computing environment with the same level of usability as on the home systems of the model. The main problem at

³ <https://research.csc.fi/csc-s-servers>

⁴ https://www.gnu.org/software/automake/manual/html_node/Autotools-Introduction.html

⁵ <https://cmake.org/>

this stage was that Cray supercomputers have a custom programming environment that requires additional treatment of environmental variables and modules, which had not been implemented in the script before. The result of the work was a modified configuration script automatically adjusting the user's environment to enable correct model installation. This helped foster portability of the MPI-ESM1 code.

The next stage was to deploy post-processing applications that were part of the model's workflow: CDO⁶, NCL⁷, and NCO⁸. To reduce the complexity of this step, we modified the workflow to eliminate NCO invocations, since it was possible to replace them with CDO invocations, and thus reduce redundancy and complexity. The installation of CDO did not result in any problems, since it has a standard building system based on Autotools. To deploy NCL, we had to tune its custom building scripts to account for the specifics of the Cray environment. This experience helped to find a more general solution for NCL installations, see D3.5, "The Handbook for SysAdmins".

The final stage was to adjust job submission scripts (sets of commands sent to the supercomputer scheduling system) according to batch job partitions on Sisu. During the testing phase we found that the job scheduler on Sisu was configured in a way that the number of user submits of jobs is inversely proportional to the priority he gets in the waiting queue. Such configurations are contrary to what is needed for efficient and fast numerical Earth System Modelling. In its default configuration the model's workflow generates one set of jobs (one computing and several post-processing) per model year. To make sure that the calculations would finish in a reasonable period, we had to reduce the number of submitted jobs, so the workflow was configured to generate one set of jobs every ten model years.

Four groups of students, each having its own numerical experiment to execute, worked with MPI-ESM1 during the summer school. According to the decision of the organisers of the summer school, taken in an effort to reduce the possibility of failures, students worked with a model at the computing facilities where the model was usually operated. Nonetheless, we chose one of the experiments, with slightly altered parameters compared to those of the model given to the students, and successfully executed the workflow of MPI-ESM1 on Sisu. The output of the calculations was provided to the students to give them an extra source of information for their research task.

FAMOUS

In the interests of expediency and efficiency, the summer school organisers chose to run remotely an installation of FAMOUS on ARCHER⁹ (the UK National HPC service) for the HadCM3 component of the course and to run associated data analysis on the RDF Analytic Cluster¹⁰ (co-located at ARCHER and with simple access to data created on ARCHER). NCAS-CMS¹¹ manage a virtual machine on the analytic cluster

⁶ <https://code.zmaw.de/projects/cdo>

⁷ <http://www.ncl.ucar.edu/>

⁸ <http://nco.sourceforge.net/>

⁹ <https://www.archer.ac.uk/>

¹⁰ <http://www.archer.ac.uk/documentation/rdf-guide/cluster.php>

¹¹ <http://cms.ncas.ac.uk/>

which supports the JASMIN analysis software stack¹² which provided the required analysis and visualisation utilities.

However, FAMOUS was deployed on the resources of the CSC as a test case. This model requires only 6 cores to run, prompting the decision to install it on the capacity machine Taito. FAMOUS had been installed on several platforms previously, but increasingly, the installation simply amounts to taking copies of infrastructure (scripts, utilities, and small executables) built at a central location for a generic x86 instruction set and loading them on the target machine. A full installation would build all this infrastructure from scratch – there are only currently a small number (possibly only one in NCAS) of support staff with the knowledge to undertake a complete installation.

We undertook the “lite” installation in an effort to better understand where difficulties arise (especially for a climate modeller with little interest in software installation) and to identify components of the process which will lend themselves to automation through a software installation package. The (lite) installation amounts to little more than copying a tarball (a compressed set of files), but even so, the specific nature of the aged FAMOUS infrastructure does not lend itself to automatic configuration and requires significant amounts of *ad hoc* manual intervention – this is an inevitable consequence of the organic nature of the development of the model.

A prerequisite to any installation is access to and in-depth knowledge of the target system. CSC provides comprehensive documentation and effective support to assist with this.

All Unified Model¹³ (UM) utilities were built for generic x86-64 architecture on an external machine and copied to Taito.

The UM infrastructure has a dependency on ksh¹⁴. The K shell on Taito behaves differently from that on ARCHER (for example) and fails to interpret “\t” and “\n” symbols as tab and carriage return. A work around for this behaviour was incorporated into the model.

FAMOUS jobs are configured through the UMUI¹⁵ which runs on PUMA (at Reading University) and not directly on Taito, and job submission is initiated from PUMA. The Taito non-interactive bash shell does not implement the module environment by default. A small modification was made to the job submission scripts to ensure that the appropriate environment was enabled for both building and running the model. The scripts explicitly load intel/16.0.0, mkl/11.3.0, intelmpi/5.1.1, and the Taito StdEnv environment modules¹⁶.

FAMOUS does have a dependency on a communications library (GCOM), which is a wrapper for MPL. The source code and configuration files for GCOM version 3.8 were copied from ARCHER, along with a version of FCM¹⁷ used to facilitate building the GCOM library. The build configuration file includes compiler flags

¹² <http://www.jasmin.ac.uk/services/jasmin-analysis-platform/>

¹³ Add reference

¹⁴ <http://www.kornshell.com>

¹⁵ **Unified Model User Interface**

¹⁶ <http://modules.sourceforge.net/>

¹⁷ <http://metomi.github.io/fcm/doc/>

appropriate for the intel FORTRAN compiler, gnu C compiler, and gmake. The GCOM library and test suite are built at the Taito command line by a single FCM command.

This part of the installation is potentially amenable to further automation. GCOM is maintained in a subversion repository (not currently accessible outside PUMA) and requires only an invocation of an FCM command to build. Testing is likewise a simple operation. FCM itself is simple to install. We attempted to develop an EasyBuild module to install and build GCOM but failed to overcome difficulties encountered in accessing the GCOM subversion code repository in the easyblock.

The build system needs to be made aware of the job submission semantics – for UM vn4.5, this happens by means of supplying so-called "hand edits" to the build infrastructure – these require significant effort to write, but are unlikely to need much additional work once specified for a particular system.

There is flexibility in how the hand edits are implemented - for this exercise, we developed the submission scripts specific to SLURM¹⁸ and applied an appropriate patch to the core UM scripts. The UMUI implements the hand edits to create scripts appropriate for Taito. An alternative and more sustainable and maintainable solution requires modification of the UMUI itself, but this is not ideal since the UMUI is not properly¹⁹ version controlled.

We conclude that FAMOUS is not a good case to consider as a candidate for automatic software installation, via the EasyBuild route for example, because it relies on technology dating from the 1980s, which predates software engineering practices open to automation. A better approach will be to develop a low resolution model based on a late UM version (10.6 for example), which installs through the highly configurable Rose Stem system²⁰ and which employs workflow and task scheduling through Cylc²¹ to manage installation, building, and running of the entire model.

Conclusions

Unfortunately, due to the constraints described above, the EC-Earth model was not deployed on the resources of CSC. To augment the work not accomplished during the school, we decided to provide the team working on the Task 3.2 with additional ideas on possible solutions for application and software stack maintenance, especially under the perspective of enabling EC-Earth for the ESiWACE demonstrators.

Many Linux distributions offer their users various package managers that help handle these issues. Using such managers, users can install software they need without diving into details of software dependencies, configuration and compilation. The problem with those package managers is that usually they are designed to work in a particular well-defined and well-tested software environment (usually with a single compiler and root privileges). This is unfortunately not the case for supercomputers. Depending on many factors (e.g. the primary scientific domain, hardware architecture, operating system, etc.), supercomputing facilities have different policies on the software stack they offer to their users by default.

¹⁸ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

¹⁹ UMUI versions are manually controlled through a simple directory structure

²⁰ <http://metomi.github.io/rose/doc/rose-rug-stem.html>

²¹ <https://cylc.github.io/cylc/>

It should be noted that the default software stack often contains custom optimized versions of the commonly used libraries, which has to be taken into account during the application deployment process, and requires additional effort to adjust the application workflow dependency trees. There are many versions and configuration options for each application and library and in addition frequently several possible compilers available to the user; all this contributes to a large combinatorial space to get lost in very easily. One of the solutions that addresses these issues is delivered by Spack²² – a package manager designed to be used on different supercomputers for software stack maintenance. We chose this software over other existing solutions for its flexibility and comprehensible code structure. The latter helped us to adjust Spack to the needs of the climate modelling community. About 20 accepted contributions to Spack’s code base have been made to enable automated deployment of applications that are part of ESM workflows.

We conclude the following from our experience working on these tasks:

- Models and other applications should be built with standard tools. The standard tools should be those targeting as broad a community as possible. This helps to develop solutions for specific situations more easily, and dramatically reduces the effort required in software deployment.
- Scripts that implement model workflows should be flexible enough to easily adjust to different scheduling systems and policies in force across different HPC facilities.
- Model workflows should be kept clean of applications which duplicate functionality.
- Installation of comprehensive system software required to satisfy model dependencies is amenable to package management
- Installation of the models themselves is less amenable to package management given the maturity and diversity in current model infrastructures. It will be advantageous in development of new models to include at the outset consideration of installation procedures for maximum portability and hence maximum usability.

²² [Hhpt://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest](https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest)